

Screening of valorisation opportunities for iron sludge from drinking water

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Abstract: During the production of drinking water, an inorganic sludge rich in iron hydroxides (iron sludge) is produced. Although this sludge is typically low in contaminants, its disposal forms a significant cost for drinking water companies. The valorisation of 2 types of iron sludge was investigated: a type originating from groundwater extraction and a type from the treatment of surface water. Based on the physical and chemical characteristics of these 2 types, we present an overview of potential applications for which iron sludge can qualify. This overview exists of both known applications and new research ideas. Next to low-grade applications (e.g. in the building industry), several more high-grade applications are also described that take into account the main strengths of iron sludge, a fine-grained material with high iron content and a strong adsorption capacity. The proposed applications are evaluated on 5 criteria: societal & environmental implications, technological feasibility, quality requirements, economics and market size.

Keywords: Iron sludge; Recovery; Potential applications

Introduction

Iron sludge is produced in the production of drinking water, both during the extraction of groundwater and the treatment of surface water. When groundwater is extracted, the water will be subjected to an aeration step, followed by sand filtration. The elements that are present in the water (e.g. Fe, Mn) will oxidize and precipitate. The precipitated sludge, rich in iron, can adsorb other elements (e.g. As). Surface water needs to be cleared from poorly sedimentable substances, colloids and part of the solutes. This is done by the addition of a flocculant, mostly FeCl₃. The resulting flocs will settle and form a sludge (i.e. iron sludge).

Iron sludge mainly contains amorphous iron hydroxides (Koopmans et al., 2010). Iron hydroxides show a strong adsorption of P and As (Pierce & Moore, 1982) (Chardon et al., 2012), but also adsorption applications for other elements (e.g. Cr) are reported (Mustafa et al., 2009).

In Flanders, iron sludge is currently disposed in three applications: biogas facilities (reaction with H₂S), agriculture (soil enhancer) and cement production (personal communication De Watergroep). Next to the use in biogas facilities, iron sludge in The Netherlands is also used in sewage treatment plants, brick production and low-grade building applications (embankment) (Personal communication De Reststoffenuie). The disposal to these applications, however, still forms a significant cost.

In this study, we will screen several valorisation opportunities for iron sludge that can create an added-value. The investigated applications (stabilisation of contaminated waste streams, biogas installations, pigment in concrete, iron reactive barriers, sewage treatment, brick production, low-grade building applications, production of FeCl₃, cement industry, agriculture) are screened and evaluated on 5 aspects: societal & environmental implications, technological feasibility, quality requirements, economics and market size.

Material and Methods

First, a screening of the characteristics of both types of iron sludge was performed. Data on total concentration of matrix elements and contaminants (closed microwave digestion with aqua regia, CMA/2/I/A.6.1, followed by ICP-AES, CMA/2/I/B.1), contaminant leaching (column leaching tests, CMA/2/II/A.9.1), pH and particle size distribution (laser diffraction) were collected. These characteristics were compared with limit values specific for each application, obtained from literature data, legislation or industrial companies.

Spectrum cards are used for visualisation and for easy comparison of different applications using a scoring system. These spectrum cards show the score (0-5) of a particular application (see example Table 1) for each individual aspect (see above) on different axes. For each application and type of iron sludge a spectrum card was drawn.

Table 1 Legend for the scores given on the aspect “market size”.

Score	Meaning
0	No market
1	Limited demand in exterior market
2	Limited demand in interior market
3	Demand < supply
4	Demand = supply
5	Demand > supply

For each aspect, a weight-factor was assigned in close collaboration with De Watergroep, allowing to rank the different proposed applications.

Results and Conclusions

When the different possible applications were ranked with the highest weight-factor for the economic potential, the top-listed applications are currently not yet in use (Table 2). These applications typically score low on their technological feasibility and therefore still need a significant investment in further research activities.

Table 2 Ranking of the applications, economic priority (50% economics, 20% market size, 15% quality requirements, 10% technological feasibility, 5% societal & environmental implications).

Application	End score
Pigment in concrete	8.1
Stabilisation of contaminated waste streams	
Use in biogas installations	7.8
Iron reactive barriers	7.1
Use in agriculture	6.7
Use in sewage treatment	6.1
Use in brick production	5.9
Use in low-grade building applications	5.2
Use in cement production	4.8
Production of FeCl ₃	4.5

For example, fine-grained iron sludges (high iron content), could be a suitable resource for concrete pigmentation. In Belgium, the total use of colour pigments in concrete is estimated to be 5-10 kton/year (rough estimation based on the extrapolation of the Belgian concrete production). The currently used primary materials cost >€600/ton. For the iron sludge to be suitable for this application, a smaller particle size needs to be obtained via grinding and the organic content of the sludge should be controlled. Although this application has a very high added-value potential, much more research in this field is still needed.

On the other hand, the use of iron sludge in biogas installations clearly is already a technically feasible application, however, the market size is rather limited and the iron sludge is often disposed of at near zero-cost.

The spectrum cards of these 2 applications are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Spectrum cards for the use of iron sludge as pigment in concrete (left) and in biogas installations (right).

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